

Research Article

**Prevalence of Insomnia in patients with Coronary Artery
Bypass Graft Surgery: A cross-sectional study from
selected region of Hamirpur, India**

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Abstract:

This cross-sectional survey was conducted over the course of a year in 2021 among people of the Indian city of Hamirpur, Himachal Pradesh, with participants selected by a convenient sampling procedure. Patients who did not use any form of medicine for their sleep problems were eligible for inclusion, but those who already had sleep disorders and used sleeping pills or psychoactive substances, or had a serious mental disease and drug addiction were excluded. Ultimately, 50 was selected for the research. Each participant completed the Insomnia Severity Index (ISI) questionnaire, which consists of five items with a total score ranging from 0 to 28. This study found that individuals had an ISI of 13 ± 6.2 before and 21 ± 2.2 after CABG. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first research to describe the prevalence of insomnia in patients undergoing CABG in this population/region. According to our findings from comparing the Insomnia Severity Index, severe problems were previously documented in patients undergoing CABG. It is because the worry of a heart attack might occur at any time prior to the CABG. After the CABG, the blockage issue in the heart attack incidence were eliminated, and the assurance of life felt rose, thus severe sleeplessness decreased significantly over time.

Keywords: CABG, prevalence, insomnia, Insomnia Severity Index(ISI)

Introduction

As a basic human need, sleep is a multidimensional, biobehavioral, and circadian process.[1] It is distinguished by the beginning of sleep, its uninterrupted duration, its duration, and its quality, which results in a feeling of refreshment upon waking up.[2] Quality of sleep, which eventually lowers the person's level of contentment with their sleep.[3] During sleep, [5] CABG patients had severely erratic breathing, and over half (67%) have sleep apnea. [6] A prolonged need for invasive mechanical ventilation, more respiratory difficulties, and an increased risk of atrial fibrillation, sepsis, and mortality have all been connected to these problems.[5-7] The existing evidence regarding the relationship between sleep apnoea and cardiovascular outcomes is derived from small studies based mainly on short-term follow-up duration.[8-12] Insomnia may be a side effect of heart failure-causing surgeries such coronary artery bypass graft surgery (CABG).[13] Because arteries and veins from other parts of the body are grafted into coronary arteries to improve the heart's blood supply, CABG is a type of surgery that bypasses blocked coronary arteries. It can be the preferred treatment for angina and reduce mortality from coronary artery blockage. [14,15] Additionally, we employed a questionnaire that asked about demographics, education, job, diabetes, marital status, sleep durability, and usage of alcohol, smokes, and sleeping pills four weeks prior to and four weeks following the operation.

METHODS

Study Design

Over the course of a year in 2021, people living in the Indian city of Hamirpur, Himachal Pradesh, participated in this cross-sectional survey. In order to determine the prevalence of insomnia before to undergo coronary artery bypass graft (CABG), the study was carried out in two phases. Data from the second stage following CABG surgery. Insomnia levels were assessed both prior to and following the CABG. All participants completed an informed

consent form, and the study protocol was approved by the institutional ethics committee. Patients with cardiac disease who were hospitalized to hospitals to undergo CABG were included in the study group. A convenient sampling method was used to choose the participants. Patients who did not use any form of medicine for their sleep problems were eligible for inclusion, but those who already had sleep disorders and used sleeping pills or psychoactive substances, or had a serious mental disease and drug addiction were excluded. Ultimately, 50 were selected for the research. Each participant completed the Insomnia Severity Index (ISI) questionnaire, which consists of five items with a total score ranging from 0 to 28. The ISI questionnaire assessed the severity of insomnia during the four weeks prior to and following the CABG. Bastien and associates designed this questionnaire.[16] Performed an initial psychometric study and demonstrated an internal consistency of $\alpha = .74$ and found item-total correlations that were quite variable, ranging from .36 to .54. Scoring Respondents rate each element of the questionnaire using Likert-type scales. Responses can range from 0 to 4, where higher scores indicate more acute symptoms of insomnia. Scores are tallied and can be compared both to scores obtained at a different phase of treatment and to the scores of other individuals. Though developers point out that their chosen cutoff scores have not been validated, they offer a few guidelines for interpreting scale results: a total score of 0–7 indicates “no clinically significant insomnia,” 8–14 means “subthreshold insomnia,” 15–21 is “clinical insomnia (moderate severity),” and 22–28 means “clinical insomnia (severe).” [Bastien et al. [16]]. The short scale is a self-report measure that takes only five minutes to complete using pencil and paper. Some participants fill out the form over the phone. Ultimately, the t-test and chi-square were used in SPSS 18 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Ill., USA) for statistical analysis. 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were included with the predicted study output.

Ethical Approval and Consent of Participants

This study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. The Research Ethics Committee of Dr. Radhakrishnan Govt. Medical College Distt. Hamirpur Himachal Pradesh, India approved the study protocol. Each participant consented to participate in the study by confirming

informed consent after being informed the purpose of the study.

RESULT

The study involved about 50 patients, 40 of whom were men [80%] and 10 of whom were women [20%]. Table 1 displays the demographic factors.

Table 1: Demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population (n = 50)

Features	n	%
Age (year) (Mean \pm standard deviation =53.36 \pm 2.259 (\pm 4.23%) CI 95%)		
40-50	19	38
51-70	31	62
Gender		
Female	10	20
Male	40	80
BMI (mean \pm standard deviation =28.49 \pm 6.10)		
\leq24.9	9	18
\geq25	41	82
Educational background		
No Schooling	12	24
Primary education	26	52
Secondary education	9	18
bachelor's level	3	6
Employment status		
No job/work	26	52
Working	24	48
Residence		
Urban	38	76
Rural	12	24
Marital Status		
Married	48	96
Widowed/divorced	1	2
Single	1	2
Alcohol use		
Yes	19	38
Never	21	42
Leaved	10	20
Smoking		
Yes	14	28
Never	13	26
Leaved	23	46

Diabetes			
	Yes	23	46
	No	27	54

BMI: Body mass index

Table 2. Distribution of mean total ISI score and severity of in insomnia of participants before and after CABG

	Before CABG n=50	After CABG n=50
Total score of ISI	13 ± 6.2	21 ± 2.2
Severity of insomnia		
No clinically significant	12	23
Subthreshold	9	6
Moderate severity	5	13
Severe	24	8

ISI, Insomnia Severity Index

Data presented as mean ± standard deviation or number

Figure1: Graphical representation of Insomnia Severity Index n=50. (refer table 2).

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to use a cross-sectional survey to explain the prevalence of insomnia events before and after the CABG. This study's participants were 50 from age 40-70, The average age of participants were 53.36 years, and most of the participants were 51-70 years 31(62%). Among the total participants Males were 40 (80%) and female participants were 10(20%) in our study.

The risk factors for sleep disruptions have been studied [17-21]. Recent investigations have looked into the connection between these and BMI [22-24]. BMI and weight reduction are therefore linked to a variety of sleep disorders, such as the diagnosis and symptoms of insomnia [24], obstructive sleep apnea [22,25], and restless legs syndrome [26], according to systematic review and meta-analysis research.

In our investigation, 9 (18%) individuals had a BMI \leq 24.9, whereas 41 (82%) had a BMI > 25. In terms of education, 26 (52%) individuals had elementary schooling, 12 (24%) did not attend school, 9 (18%) finished secondary education, and 3 (6%) received a degree. Among all participants, 26 (52%) were retired or unemployed, while 24 (48%) were working. 38 (76%) of the participants resided in cities, whereas 12 (24%) lived in rural areas. The majority of them were married, 48 (96%) were widowed/divorced, and one (2%) was single.

Insomnia, or sleep disruption, is common with alcohol dependency. The prevalence estimates range between 36-91%. [27-31]

We identified alcoholism among individuals; 19 (38%) were current drinkers, 13 (26%) never drank, and 23 (46%) stopped drinking during the first year. It is generally documented that smoking causes sleep disruptions. Smokers have less total sleep time, difficulties beginning sleep, more fragmented sleep, and more light sleep than nonsmokers, as evidenced by both objective sleep measures using polysomnography [32,33] and subjectively reported symptoms [34-38]. Smoking is linked to many sleep disorders, including obstructive sleep apnea [39] and restless legs syndrome [40]. In terms of smoking, there were 14 current smokers (28%), 13 never smokers (26%), and 23 former smokers (46%).

Clinical study indicates that up to one-third of diabetic patients experience sleep disturbances, compared to 8.2% of non-diabetic controls [41]. According to a University of Pittsburgh research survey, more than half of people with type 2 diabetes are likely to report being "poor sleepers". Patients with type 2 DM were more likely to have low Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) [42].

Among participants 23 (46%) were diabetic and 27 (54%) were non-diabetic. Table 2 summarizes the study of the mean score on the 5 items of ISI, i.e. distribution of mean total ISI score and severity of insomnia among participants before and after CABG. The total mean score of ISI was 13 ± 6.2 before and 21 ± 2.2 after CABG. Prior to the CABG, 12

patients had no clinically significant insomnia, 9 had subthreshold insomnia, 5 had moderate severity, and 24 had severe insomnia.

Following 4 weeks the CABG, 23 participants had no clinically significant symptoms, 6 had subthreshold symptoms, 13 had moderate intensity symptoms, and 8 had severe sleeplessness. The factors that cause sleep disruption during hospitalization and one month after discharge are different. Insomnia following CABG is a significant condition with a high incidence that affects patients' quality of life and daily function. Some studies suggest that an educational intervention-based paradigm that integrates identified sleep mediators and comprehensive rehabilitation programs in cardiac rehabilitation clinics can enhance sleep quality following CABG.[43]

The study's limitations were a less number of items on the questionnaire and a lack of follow-up for some patients following surgery. Because the participants are not available at home or there are issues with the internet network.

Conclusion:

This study found that individuals had an ISI of 13 ± 6.2 before and 21 ± 2.2 after CABG. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first research to describe the prevalence of insomnia in patients undergoing CABG in this population/region. According to our findings from comparing the Insomnia Severity Index, severe problems were previously documented in patients undergoing CABG. It is because the worry of a heart attack might occur at any time prior to the CABG. After the CABG, the blockage issue in the heart attack incidence were eliminated, and the assurance of life felt rose, thus severe sleeplessness decreased significantly over time. Following the CABG, participants report improved quality of life. We recommend that patients' families use behavioral or medication for the management of sleep disruptions in order to successfully reduce the effects of insomnia.

Authors' contributions

All authors contributed significantly to the study's design, data collecting, and result interpretation. All of the authors made significant contributions to critically editing the work for crucial intellectual content and approving the final version for publication.

Declaration of competing interest

All the authors declare that the submitted article is not related to any financial interest/relationship.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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